

Microstructure and relative humidity effects on long-term indentation creep properties of calcium carbonate cement

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Abstract

This paper addresses the effect of both microstructure and relative humidity on the long-term creep properties of sustainable calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) cements. The cements are prepared by mixing amorphous calcium carbonate and vaterite with water. A larger starting amount of vaterite, X_v , within the mixture design gives a higher elasticity and resistance to the specimens due to the larger overall bridging area within the newly formed calcite crystals. Regarding creep properties for a given relative humidity, the amplitude of creep strain decreases with X_v , and makes the relation between the elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , of the samples to be linear with the contact creep modulus, C . On the other hand, for a given composition, the amplitude of creep increases with the relative humidity, making the contact creep modulus, C_i , to rise exponentially with the elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , of the specimens. The most probable creep mechanisms for this kind of cement seem to be a combination of microcracking in the early stages and dissolution and reprecipitation of calcite in the long-term (also known as pressure solution theory). The presence of water in pores with increasing relative humidity might enhance the local dissolution of calcite, and hence the creep amplitude.

Keywords: Calcium carbonate cement, compressive strength, creep, micro-indentation, microstructure, relative humidity.

1. Introduction

Due to the carbon footprint of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) there has been an increased interest in alternative hydraulic binders [1–4]. Among natural cements, one of the most common is calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) but despite of its abundance, very few have reported its use as an artificial cementing agent for engineering purposes. For example, companies like Calera Corporation [5], Novacem [6] and Solidia Tech [7] have developed different technologies to make binders from precipitated carbonates. More specifically, they capture and mineralize CO₂ through aqueous precipitation using solutions rich on calcium [8,9], magnesium [10] or a mixture of calcium and silica [11] ions, respectively. The precipitates are optimum supplementary cementitious materials to replace up to 95% of Portland clinker for some specific applications [12].

Previously, *Molenaar & Venmans* [13], inspired by the method introduced by *Cailleau* [14], proposed a methodology to bond soil particles by calcium carbonate crystals. More specifically, they proposed the recirculation of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ solution, pumped by CO_2 , through the sample aiming to cement. As the solution pass through the sample, CaCO_3 encounter suitable nucleating sites among the host grains and work as a bonding agent. A commercially version of this methodology was tested by *Ismail et al.* [15] with different soils including glass beads, calcareous sand and silica sand. However, this approach requires soil casting under sealed conditions to flush the starting solution, making it absolutely unpractical to apply on site in comparison with paste options. Another environmentally friendly example was introduced by BioCement Technologies [16]. In their approach, soil particles are also bond to each other by calcium carbonate particles, but those are precipitated by the action of bacteria strains when they have access to urea and calcium salt. Although this approach, commonly known as microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP), has already been applied to bond several kind of soils [17–19], its potential application is limited to precast construction materials for practical and time-processing reasons.

Beside all these examples, the first entirely pure CaCO_3 cement paste, with similar mouldable and malleable properties as ordinary Portland cement (OPC) pastes was synthesized by *Fontaine et al.* [20] and *Combes et al.* [21]. They mixed water with two CaCO_3 solid phases: one was the highly reactive amorphous calcium carbonate, ACC, while the other was one of the metastable crystalline phases, either vaterite, V, or aragonite, Ar, which acted as a seed for their (re)crystallization into the most stable calcite polymorph during the setting reaction.

Due to environmental benefits of CaCO_3 cement, i.e. no CO_2 production, low energetic costs, etc., in comparison with OPC, we aim at further characterizing and analysing its mechanical properties, especially the compressive strength and creep deformation, before considering a commercial upgrade.

Undoubtedly, the compressive strength is the most relevant property that engineers and architects needs to know to design and calculate structures built on this material. *Combes et al.* [21] reported values within 3-13 MPa for CaCO_3 pastes with diverse microstructures, but the effect of the mixture design on the mechanical properties still requires further understanding.

Another property that demands significant analysis before up-grading CaCO_3 cements to commercial production is its long term deformation. Since the classical experiments of *Phillips* [22] and *Andrade* [23], considerable interest has been given to creep deformation, which stands for slow deformation of materials at constant stress conditions with respect to time. Moreover, the importance of taking creep deformation into consideration in the design of structures was recalled recently since it may cause deflection and curvature, cracking and redistribution of stresses [24,25]. Creep in polycrystalline aggregates such as CaCO_3 cement usually evolves through three stages: an initial transient phase with decelerating strain rate, a second steady state creep and a final accelerating creep phase [26]. Several models have been proposed to describe these phases [27–29] but hardly any take explicitly into account the effects of dissolution, which is important in compaction creep of wet, fine grained, porous materials. *Keszthelyi et al.* [30], however, presented a novel micromechanical approach to describe transient creep of rocks with fluid-filled pores by the combined effect

of fracturing and pressure solution. Creep of cementitious materials is a complex issue and it is still difficult to predict in the long-term since it is often coupled with other phenomena such as hydration and drying, while it can be influenced by several parameters such as temperature, seasonal moisture changes, level of stress, water content and mixture design simultaneously.

Since cementitious materials are multi-scale porous materials, creep is largely influenced by the presence of water in porosity and therefore by moisture changes. Multiple studies have already pointed out the necessity of controlling the moisture equilibrium of the samples before creep evaluation. For instance, *Pickett* [31] found that ordinary concrete under load and being dried at same time presented a higher deformation than that of a sample under load without drying. Moreover, *Tamtsia and Beaudoin* [32] found that the history of drying also influence the basic creep of cement pastes. The amplitude of creep was lower for those samples which set without drying. As a consequence, radically different interpretations of experimental data, and therefore theories, have been proposed to rationalize creep of cementitious materials [33–36]. Although most authors agree to point out that the origin of long-term creep in OPC lies in the amorphous calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H) phase [37,38], we aim at unravelling the mechanisms for pure crystalline carbonate systems without this amorphous phase and at comparing the results with state-of-the-art creep models [30].

In the present study, free-CO₂, 100% pure calcium carbonate cements have been synthesized at laboratory scale following *Combes* method [21] as a proxy to investigate the effect of both microstructure and moisture on long-term basic creep behaviour of pure calcium carbonate materials. The effect of microstructure is studied by preparing and testing samples with varied mixture design while the effect of moisture is studied by conditioning and testing those compositions in various relative humidity (RH) conditions. Creep experiments have been carried out over hardened samples with the micro-indentation technique validated for long-term basic creep [39].

2. Materials and methods

CaCO₃ cement samples with diverse mixture design (varied amorphous to vaterite, ACC:V, weight percent, wt%, ratio) have been prepared and conditioned at different relative humidities (RH). After setting, a first set of samples have been used to evaluate their compressive strength using uniaxial compressive strength tests, while a second set have been used to assess their long-term creep deformation properties via micro-indentation (μ -indentation) tests.

2.1. Preparation of CaCO₃ reagent powders and cement samples

The preparation of CaCO₃ cements requires the synthesis of different calcium carbonate polymorphs in order to design the initial cement mixture [21]. Accordingly, both ACC and vaterite phases were prepared as described in [40]. Briefly, they were precipitated by double decomposition between calcium chloride (CaCl₂·6H₂O, Sigma Aldrich) and sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃, Sigma Aldrich) equimolar (0.5 M) solutions at room temperature using a magnetic stirrer set at 400 rpm. The reaction time was just 10 sec for ACC and 30 min for vaterite taking as a reference *Ogino et al.* studies [41]. To wash off any dissolved sodium chloride (NaCl), the CaCO₃ precipitates were rinsed under vacuum with deionized water and ethanol, using a

filtering kit and 0.5 μm pore-size filter papers (Millipore, USA). Subsequently, the CaCO_3 precipitates were flushed with liquid N_2 to block any evolution of these metastable phases. The frozen precipitates were lyophilized (Alpha 1-4 LD plus, Martin Christ, Germany) for 48 h at 0.05 mbars and -50°C and stored in a freezer (-22°C) with additional silica powder bags prior to cement manufacturing.

The precipitates were scanned by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Bruker D8 Discover X-ray diffractometer) to identify the crystalline phases present using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation (30 mA and 40 kV) and recording 2θ angles from 20 to 50° at a 0.04 s^{-1} sweep rate. Additionally, they were imaged with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Hitachi SU5000 Field-Emission; 1kV acceleration voltage and 3.0 mm working distance).

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of the oedometric press designed to cast CaCO_3 cements. The main body is a metallic hollow cylinder (12.0 cm in height and 2.0 cm inner diameter) coated with Teflon[®] spray. The cement paste is compacted between two porous plastic discs and the assembly is loaded by a steel spring with the aid of two plastic stoppers at the edges.

CaCO_3 cements with different microstructures were synthesized by mixing ACC and vaterite powders in different weight ratios (wt.%): 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3, respectively, with distilled water keeping a water-to-powder ratio, w/p , of 0.5. Just after mixing the powders with the liquid phase, the resulting pastes were viscous and easily mouldable for several minutes and they were placed in specially designed oedometric presses (Figure

1) in between two porous, plastic-made, auxiliary discs. The inner walls of the presses were coated with Teflon ®. A steel spring loaded the assembly uniaxially. Using the spring constant of the spring and the surface of the auxiliary discs it was estimated that the sample was under a stress value of approximately 0.15 MPa. The specimens were unmolded after 24 h and left under atmospheric conditions for final drying (21 °C, ~55% RH). This process was followed by means of their weight evolution using digital scales (Sartorius Lab Instruments, Germany, accuracy = 0.1 mg). After 28 days of drying, a first set of samples were cut into smaller cylinders using a metallic saw and polishing paper (silicon carbide P80D) brought to 1.00 ± 0.02 cm in height and 0.50 ± 0.02 cm in diameter to perform compressive strength tests, while a second set were brought to 1.00 ± 0.02 cm in height and 2.00 ± 0.02 cm in diameter to carry out μ -indentation tests. The final dimensions of the specimens were measured using a calliper and used to determine their apparent density, ρ_a . To ensure reproducibility, sufficient cement quantities were made to perform all analyses on the same sample batch.

2.2. Uniaxial compressive strength tests

To evaluate the elastic modulus, E , and the uniaxial compressive yield strength, Y , of hardened CaCO_3 cement compositions prepared as described on the previous section (cylinders with 1.00 ± 0.02 cm in height and 0.50 ± 0.02 cm in diameter), uniaxial compression tests were carried out using a DEBEN CT5000 (UK) tensile/compression stage (5000 N load cell, 0.01 N resolution), at a crosshead speed of 0.2 mm/min, corresponding to strain rates of 10^{-3} s^{-1} . Three samples of each composition were tested to ensure repeatability.

2.2.1. Data analysis

From the recorded data (applied force and elongation), a stress–strain curve was constructed for each test. Figure 2 shows an example stress-strain curve constructed for one of the indentations performed at 54% RH to a specimen with a starting composition ACC:V = 1:3 wt.%.

Figure 2. Stress-strain, σ - ϵ , curve constructed from the applied force and elongation recorded during uniaxial compressive test of a CaCO_3 cement sample with a starting composition ACC:V = 1:3 wt.%, conditioned and tested at 54% RH. The red solid line represents the best fit performed to determine the elastic modulus, E , of the sample while the dashed arrow indicates its compressive strength, Y .

As shown, the initial relationship between the stress and the strain follows a curved trend which can be explained as a geometrical re-adjustment between the sample and the machine's jaws typically due to a lack of parallelism within the sample's top and bottom surfaces. Eventually, the relationship become linear being the elastic modulus, E , the proportional factor between the two parameters: $\sigma = E \cdot \varepsilon$. Consequently, the elastic modulus, E , can be calculated from the slope of this linear region.

With increasing stress, the sample begins to deform plastically and the curve deviates from linearity. This point is known as the yield point and represents the compressive yield strength, Y , of the specimen. The dashed arrow on Figure 2 indicates the yield stress. Both the elastic modulus, E , and compressive strength, Y , were extracted from the curves using an in-house developed script in Matlab®.

2.3. Micro-indentation creep experiments

2.3.1. Sample conditioning

Prior to μ -indentation tests, one specimen of each composition was moved into a desiccator with a controlled relative humidity (RH) for conditioning. The RH conditions were created by filling the desiccators with saturated aqueous salt solutions sufficient time in advance to equilibrate the desiccator atmosphere before moving the samples in. More specifically, the chemicals MgCl_2 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and KNO_3 were used to create RH of 33%, 54% and 93%, respectively, at the temperature of 23 °C [42].

In order to determine the duration of conditioning necessary for the samples to achieve moisture equilibrium with conditioning environment, the mass evolution of the three different samples being conditioned at 33% RH were measured in parallel with sample conditioning.

The measurements showed very similar drying kinetics for the three compositions, which required 3 days to achieve moisture equilibrium with conditioning environment. Consequently, all samples were let for 5 days inside the desiccators to ensure total moisture equilibrium at each RH prior to microindentation creep experiments. Under these conditions, autogenous shrinkage during creep tests is avoided and hence the contact creep compliance, $L(t)$, only characterizes basic creep, i.e., the deformation of the samples is exclusively due to the application of an external mechanical load.

2.3.2. Measurement protocol

Microindentation creep experiments were carried out using the load-controlled indentation apparatus in Lafarge-Holcim Research Center (France) [43]. It is equipped with a load-head motor, a force sensor, a displacement sensor, a controller-monitoring system, an indentation platform and a removable chamber for relative humidity control during indentation tests.. Using a closed feedback loop, the instrument controls the applied load and records the evolution of the indentation depth. Prior to the experiments, the microindenter was calibrated according to the ASTM standard E 2546-07 [44] and its compliance was determined according to *Kalidindi et al.* [45].

After sample conditioning, microindentation creep experiments were carried out in relative-humidity-controlled environment by circulating air with controlled RH inside the indentation chamber. The air was obtained by pumping dry CO_2 -free air into saturated salts solutions [43].

On each sample, 10 microindentation tests were performed on a different location with a Vickers indenter probe, a square-based diamond pyramid having an angle of 136 degrees between faces. With this geometry, its shape area function, $A_c(h_c)$, i.e., the relationship between the indentation depth when it is in contact with the sample, h_c , and the projected contact area, A_c , is the following:

$$A_c(h_c) = 24.5 h_c^2 \quad (1)$$

The maximal force applied, F_{max} , for all experiments was 1 N, which according to previous studies [46–48], is low enough to ensure proportionality between creep strain and applied stress. For each indent, the load was increased linearly over time at a rate equal to 10 N/min, kept constant during the holding phase, and decreased linearly over time back to zero at the same rate as the loading one. Out of the 10 indents performed on each sample, 5 were with a relatively short 20-sec-long holding phase, while 5 were performed with a relatively long 180-sec-long holding phase.

2.3.3. Data analysis

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the indentation depth, h , with the applied load, F , recorded from a microindentation test performed on a sample with an starting composition ACC:V = 1:1 wt.%, conditioned and tested at 54% RH. In this figure, $h = 0$ stands for the onset of contact between the indentation probe and the sample. Moreover, the three phases of the test – loading, holding and unloading – are represented with different colours to facilitate their identification.

Figure 3. Indentation load, F , as function of indentation depth, h , recorded during a microindentation experiment over a CaCO_3 sample with an starting composition ACC:V = 1:1 wt.% previously conditioned at 54% RH. The quantities shown are: the peak indentation load, F_{max} , the indenter maximum displacement at peak load, h_{max} , the final depth of the contact impression after unloading, h_f , and the unloading stiffness of the sample, S .

2.3.3.1. Assessment of time-independent properties

The mechanical problem involved in indentation testing is a typical problem of contact mechanics: the indentation probe penetrates into a flat surface of a material of interest and then is withdrawn from the

surface. *Galini et al.* [49] presented, for the first time, a solution for the indentation of an elastic half-space by a rigid axisymmetric indentation probe. By adapting its theory for a Vickers indenter probe, the following equation links the indentation load, F , to indentation depth, h , via the effective modulus, E_{eff} , and the indenter geometry coefficient, g :

$$F = \varphi \cdot E_{eff} \cdot h^{1+1/g} \quad (2)$$

where φ represents a constant parameter which includes the *Euler Gamma* function. A differentiation of the equation above with respect to the indentation depth, h , gives [50]:

$$S = \frac{dF}{dh} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot E_{eff} \cdot \sqrt{A_c} \quad (3)$$

where S is the contact stiffness defined by $S = dF/dh$, and A_c is the projected contact area (or briefly, contact area) between the indentation probe and the indented surface. Moreover, the effective modulus, E_{eff} , can be linked to the Elastic modulus, E , by the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{E_{eff}} = \frac{1 - \nu_{in}^2}{E_{in}} + \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E} \quad (4)$$

where ν_{in} and ν are the *Poisson's* ratio of the indentation probe and that of the tested material, respectively; E_{in} and E are the Elastic modulus of the indentation probe and that of the tested material, respectively. For a rigid indentation probe, Eq. 4 can be simplified as the following, in which M is termed as the indentation modulus:

$$E_{eff} \cong \frac{E}{1 - \nu^2} = M \quad (5)$$

Another time-independent property which can be assessed is the indentation hardness, H . It is defined as the average pressure below the indenter and can be calculated with the following equation:

$$H = \frac{F_{max}}{A_c} \quad (6)$$

Consequently, the short (20-sec-long) holding phase tests enabled us to determine the Elastic modulus, E , with Eq. 3 and Eq. 5 and the hardness, H , with Eq. 6, of the different cement compositions assuming a *Poisson's* ratio $\nu = 0.20$ for all of them.

2.3.3.1.1. Determination of the projected contact area, A_c : the Oliver and Pharr method

To determine the Elastic modulus, E , and the hardness, H , we need to find out the projected contact area, A_c . In the present study, the method introduced by *Oliver and Pharr* [51] has been used. As presented on Figure 4, in this method the indentation depth, h , can be decomposed into two parts: a depth h_c over which the indentation probe is in contact with the indented surface and a depth h_s over which the probe is not in contact with the indented surface:

$$h = h_c + h_s \quad (7)$$

Figure 4. Schematic representation of a section through an indentation showing various parameters used in Oliver and Pharr method, schematic adapted from [51].

Applying the solution of *Sneddon* [52] for a conical indentation probe, the depth h_s over which the probe is not in contact with the indented surface can be linked to the residual depth h_f of the indent after withdrawing the indentation probe (See Figure 3):

$$h_s = \frac{\pi - 2}{\pi} \cdot (h - h_f) = \frac{\pi - 2}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{F}{S} \quad (8)$$

Deriving from *Sneddon's* load-displacement relation expressed in Eq. 2 and applying it for a conical indentation probe yields:

$$h_c = h_{max} - 0.72 \cdot \frac{F_{max}}{S_{max}} \quad (9)$$

where $S_{max} = \left. \frac{dF}{dh} \right|_{F=F_{max}}$ is the maximum contact stiffness at the maximum load. Thus, Eq. 9 offers a method to estimate the contact depth between indenter and indented surface and it can be used to determine the projected contact area, A_c .

2.3.3.2. Assessment of time-dependent properties

Indentation tests can also be used to measure the creep properties of materials. By introducing a fictitious indentation test with an instantaneous loading phase, an instantaneous unloading phase and an instantaneous-reloading-and holding phase, *Vandamme et al.* [53] derived a method to back-calculate creep properties from an indentation test in which time-independent plasticity occurs (See Supplementary Material).

The main assumption in their derivation is that time independent plasticity occurs only during the loading phase but not during the holding nor unloading phases. Under this assumption and making use of the *Oliver and Pharr's* method [51], the authors proposed the following equation:

$$L(t) - L(0) = L(t) - \frac{1}{M_0} = \frac{2 r_c \Delta h(t)}{F_{max}} \quad (10)$$

where $L(t)$ is the contact creep compliance, $L(0)$ is the reciprocal of the indentation modulus at the moment of loading, r_c is the radius of the contact area, A_c , and $\Delta h(t)$ is the change of indentation depth during the

holding phase. The difference $L(t) - L(0)$ is termed the contact creep function and it can be back-calculated to obtain the contact creep compliance, $L(t)$, which is a material property.

Thus, 180-sec-long holding phase indents were used in the present study to measure the change of indentation depth, $\Delta h(t)$, during the holding phase using the following equation:

$$\Delta h(t) = (h(t) - F_{max} C_m) - (h(t=0) - F_{max} C_m) \quad (11)$$

where C_m is the machine compliance determined according to *Kalidindi et al.* [45]. In this equation, $t = 0$ refers to the onset of the holding phase. Thus, by introducing in Eq. 10 the user-set value for the applied load, $F_{max} = 1 \text{ N}$, and the radius of contact, r_c , calculated from Eq. 1 and Eq. 9, the contact creep function, $L(t) - L(0)$, could be back-calculated for each test.

Moreover, since the contact creep function (Eq. 10) has been proved to be logarithmic with respect to time [54,55], it could be fitted to the following equation, which allowed a quantitative comparison of the characteristic parameters of each sample:

$$L(t) - \frac{1}{M_0} = \frac{\ln(t/\tau_i + 1)}{C_i} \quad (12)$$

where the fitting parameters C_i represents the contact creep modulus and τ_i is the characteristic creep time. The former provides an idea about the amplitude of the creep function, so that low creep rates are represented by large creep modulus values, while the latter represent the length of the transient period required to reach the logarithmic kinetics of creep. It is worth mentioning that the characteristic creep time, τ , is not a universal parameter but depends on the applied stress. Nevertheless, since we have applied the same stress to all compositions, their characteristic creep time, τ , values are still comparable.

3. Results and discussion

The synthesized amorphous calcium carbonate, ACC, and vaterite, V, polymorphs, necessary to manufacture CaCO_3 cements are introduced. Afterwards, the elasticity and the compressive strength of the set cement samples are presented and discussed. Finally, the elastic and creep strain results obtained from microindentation tests are shown as function of the mixture design and moisture equilibrium with relative humidity. Some possible creep mechanisms controlling creep deformation of CaCO_3 cements are also introduced and discussed.

3.1. Characterization of CaCO_3 precipitates

As shown in [40], ACC precipitates (Figure 5A) consist of equidimensional spherical nanoparticles (<50 nm in diameter) accompanied by rhombohedral crystals of about 50-100 nm. These are interpreted to be calcite and confirmed by XRD analysis (Figure 5C). Vaterite precipitates (Figure 5B) consist of spherical grains of 4-5 μm in diameter also accompanied by rhombohedral grains (4-5 μm), which are calcite according to the XRD scans (Figure 5C). Both ACC and vaterite precipitates are about 90% pure (from XRD analysis) with only minor amounts of calcite.

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of synthesized calcium carbonate powders in the form of (a) ACC phase and (b) Vaterite phase. (c) XRD patterns of (a) and (b) powders.

3.2. Elasticity and strength of CaCO_3 cement

The elastic modulus, E , and the compressive yield strength, Y , of CaCO_3 cement samples with different initial compositions (ACC:V = 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.%) have been calculated from uniaxial compressive tests carried out at ambient conditions (54% RH). The obtained values are summarized in Table 1, while their main variations are included on Figure 7C and D as function of the initial vaterite content, X_V , i.e., both series have been rescaled by their maximum value to show their main trend.

From Figure 7C and D, one observes that a larger starting amount of vaterite, X_V , results in specimens with higher elastic modulus and yield strength. Indeed, both E and Y are linear in X_V : $E = 0.029 \cdot X_V - 0.560$ GPa and $Y = 0.091 \cdot X_V - 1.462$ MPa.

The origin of this behaviour seems to be related to the recrystallization kinetics that we have recently published [40]. We characterized the kinetics of recrystallization of ACC and vaterite phases into calcite and the rigidity development (storage modulus) during setting of CaCO_3 pastes with the same mixture design as the ones tested here (ACC:V = 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.%). We found that the characteristic times for building up the storage modulus of the cement pastes increased linearly with the characteristic time of recrystallization. The higher the initial vaterite content, X_V , the faster recrystallization and the faster build-up of rigidity in the paste.

We suggested “crystal bridging” [56] as the mechanism ruling the structural development of the pastes during the setting reaction and it could be deduced that a faster (re)crystallization process, induced by a larger initial amount of vaterite, enhanced the bridging mechanism during setting. We hypothesized that a larger initial amount of vaterite induced contacting of calcite crystals at earlier stages and subsequent crystal growth resulted on joints with a larger contact area and stronger contacts. From Figure 7C and D, one observes that our previous hypothesis agrees well with the trends presented here for the elastic modulus and the compressive strength.

Furthermore, the aim of our previous study [40] was not to study different protocols for preparing the strongest hardened cement, but rather to systematically study dependence of the strength evolution with recrystallization at a practically attainable density.

The apparent density, ρ_a , of all compositions here prepared (ACC:V = 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.%) is within $1.66 \pm 0.06 \text{ g/cm}^3$ regardless of their initial design. Comparing this value with the density of pure calcite (2.71

g/cm^3) [57], a porosity, ϕ , of about 39 % can be deduced for all of them. It is known that Young's modulus of the natural CaCO_3 cements limestone and chalk depends exponentially on porosity [58]. At 39% porosity chinks and limestones have a Young's modulus of 7 GPa compared to 0.1-3 GPa in this study. The yield stress of 40% porosity wet chalk was found to be in the range 7-10 MPa in hydrostatic tests [59], that corresponds to 2-4 MPa in uniaxial tests which is similar to the results obtained for the cements presented here. This signifies that the elasticity and yield of our samples are in the expected range for high porosity small grain size calcium carbonate cement. Changing the preparation procedure to produce lower the porosity is expected to increase the strength exponentially. It also seems feasible to enhance the cement strength by bringing the pastes under pressure during the setting reaction. For example, Ishikawa *et al.* [60] interconnected calcite granules by exposing them to acidic calcium phosphate solutions under different pressures. The compressive strength of the set aggregates increases with the loading stress during setting until a critical value, above which the intermediate phase cannot be formed in between the granules resulting in weaker bonds.

3.3. Microindentation experiments on CaCO_3 cement

The creep properties of CaCO_3 cement samples with different initial composition (ACC:V = 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.%) and moisture equilibrium with the atmosphere (RH = 33, 54 and 93%) have been investigated via microindentation tests. Figure 6A shows the recorded evolution of the indentation depth, Δh , with time, t , during the holding phase (180-sec-long) of indentation experiments performed on CaCO_3 cement samples with dissimilar starting compositions but all conditioned and tested at 54 % RH. In this figure, $t = 0$ s stands for the onset of the holding phase and the corresponding indentation depth, h , is normalized to 0 mm. The measurements recorded for CaCO_3 cement samples conditioned and tested at 33 and 93% RH are not shown for simplicity.

Figure 6. A) Indentation depth, Δh , as function of time during the holding phase of microindentation tests performed on CaCO_3 cement samples with diverse starting composition (ACC:V = 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.%) all conditioned at 54% RH, and B) Calculated contact creep functions $L(t) - 1/M_0$ using Eq. 10. For each sample, out of the 5 experiments performed, only the median curve is displayed. The dashed lines represent the best fits to Eq. 12.

As observed, the indentation depth reached during the holding phase decreases for samples with a larger amount of vaterite, X_V , within the initial cement mixture design. Figure 6B shows the contact creep functions, $L(t) - 1/M_0$, yielded by the three different CaCO_3 cement samples; calculated from Eq. 10. The results show that for a given relative humidity, the amplitude of creep decreases with the initial amount of vaterite, X_V . Moreover, the results show that the assumption that creep is logarithmic with respect to time seems justified and conforms well with long-term basic creep behaviour of other cementitious materials [34,38]. Moreover, the results also confirm that minute-long microindentation creep experiments are long enough to reach the long-term creep behaviour of crystalline cement pastes, as it was demonstrated before for amorphous ones [39]. Consequently, Figure 6B also shows the best fits obtained using Eq. 12 (yellow dashed lines) to get the characterizing parameters for every composition and environmental condition tested. Table 1 includes a summary of these results as function of the relative humidity and the initial mixture design (ACC:V wt.%). Moreover, the elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , values calculated from 20-sec-long microindentation tests are also included. The main variations of all measured parameters are included on Figure 7 as function of the initial vaterite content, X_V , (A-D) and relative humidity, RH (E-H). In order to show the main trend, each parameter has been rescaled by its maximum value in each series. All subplots have the same scale except C/C_{\max} versus RH (subplot E) which is plotted as a semilog plot due to the exponential variation. The black whole drawn lines are fit to all the data in the subplots and show the main trend of the data.

Table 1. Elastic modulus, E , and compressive strength, Y , of CaCO_3 cement samples obtained from uniaxial compressive strength tests at 54 % RH. Contact creep modulus, C_i , characteristic creep time, τ , elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , of CaCO_3 cement samples conditioned and tested at 33%, 54% and 93% RH, obtained from microindentation tests.

Relative Humidity	Sample		Uniaxial compression tests		Microindentation tests			
RH (%)	Initial ACC:V (wt.%)	water/powder ratio	E [GPa]	Y[MPa]	C_i [GPa]	τ [s]	E [GPa]	H [MPa]
33	1:1	0.5	-	-	8.15 ± 1.33	2.46 ± 0.04	1.48 ± 0.44	16.73 ± 1.54
	1:2	0.5	-	-	45.10 ± 7.30	1.59 ± 0.89	1.77 ± 0.40	18.46 ± 1.12
	1:3	0.5	-	-	82.71 ± 16.40	0.57 ± 0.03	1.79 ± 0.58	20.73 ± 0.88
54	1:1	0.5	0.97 ± 0.43	3.13 ± 0.78	1.17 ± 0.32	7.39 ± 0.89	0.84 ± 0.15	5.89 ± 1.01
	1:2	0.5	1.36 ± 0.30	4.55 ± 0.90	5.51 ± 0.44	2.05 ± 0.84	1.66 ± 0.49	13.30 ± 1.85
	1:3	0.5	1.69 ± 0.19	5.43 ± 0.72	9.97 ± 1.31	1.55 ± 0.32	2.51 ± 0.58	18.05 ± 2.15
93	1:1	0.5	-	-	0.053 ± 0.008	18.06 ± 1.06	0.078 ± 0.024	3.17 ± 0.59
	1:2	0.5	-	-	0.075 ± 0.012	12.07 ± 1.32	0.882 ± 0.052	3.66 ± 1.19
	1:3	0.5	-	-	0.135 ± 0.017	7.06 ± 2.63	1.030 ± 0.179	3.78 ± 0.31

Figure 7. Main variations of measured parameters with initial vaterite content, X_V (A-D) and relative humidity, RH (E-H). In order to show the main trend, each parameter has been rescaled by its maximum value in each series. All subplots have the same scale except C/C_{max} versus RH (subplot E) which is plotted as a semilog plot due to the exponential variation. The black whole drawn lines are fit to all the data in the subplots and show the main trend of the data. The slope of the lines is indicated in each subplot. The insert in the bottom right plot (subplot H) shows that hardness, H , increases linearly with Young's modulus, E .

3.3.1. Effect of mixture design and creep mechanisms

Figure 7(A-D) shows the main variations of all measured parameters (contact creep modulus, C_i , characteristic creep time, τ_i , elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H) from microindentation tests as function of the initial vaterite content, X_V , of samples conditioned and tested at three different RH. At a glance, Figure 7A shows that the contact creep modulus, C_i , of CaCO_3 cement samples increases linearly with X_V , for all RH conditions. For example, at 54% RH the contact creep modulus, C_i , raises from about 1 GPa for the sample initially containing ~50% of vaterite up to 10 GPa for the cement with the largest vaterite concentration, i.e., an increase by factor 10. The average for all RH trends has a slope of 3.1. On the other hand, the characteristic creep time, τ_i , decreases linearly with X_V for all tested RH, being the slope of the averaged trend of about the same order but with the opposite effect (-2.9). Thus, both parameters seem to be linearly coupled with X_V for all RH conditions.

The effect of X_V on the elastic modulus, E , and the hardness, H , of CaCO_3 cement samples conditioned at different RH is shown on Figure 7C and D, respectively. At a glance, one observes that both follow a similar drift as the one obtained for the contact creep modulus, C_i ; i.e., a larger starting amount of vaterite, X_V , results in specimens with higher E and H , being their relationship approximately linear for all RH. Moreover, as introduced on previous section, these subplots also include the main variations for the elastic modulus, E , and the compressive yield strength, Y , measured from uniaxial compression tests. One observes, that the uniaxial compression tests results conform well with the trends obtained from microindentation

experiments, being the two-tailed P value between them of 0.6469, which by conventional criteria is not statistically significant (See Table 1).

Even though C_i , E and H rise linearly with X_V , their average trends are significantly different. The effect of X_V is more evident on C_i , (slope of 3.1), followed by E , (slope of 2.4), and finally on H , (slope of 1.4). A comparative study of the two moduli (C_i and E) yields a linear relationship, as shown on Figure 8. All data points nicely align around $E_i = 0.618 \cdot C_i + 0.180$ GPa. The evolution of H with C_i also follows a linear relationship: $H_i = 0.0046 \cdot C_i + 0.0012$ GPa. Thus, both E and H rise linearly with C_i . Nevertheless, these relationships differ from the ones observed for C-S-H phases also obtained by nanoindentation tests: *Vandamme and Ulm* [61] also found a linear relation between C_i and H , but a power law relation between C_i and E , highlighting the differences on creep behaviour between amorphous (C-S-H) and crystalline (CaCO_3) cements.

Figure 8. Contact creep modulus, C_i , versus elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , for CaCO_3 cements with diverse ACC:V initial mixtures and in moisture equilibrium with 54% RH.

Since all CaCO_3 cement samples were prepared with the same water-to-powder ratio ($w/p = 0.5$) and, as recalled on the previous section, all have a similar porosity, the differences among their creep functions must be due to their particular microstructure, i.e., composition and volume fraction of each phase, and specially due to the joint's strength among CaCO_3 grains after setting. This hypothesis agrees again well with our previous findings about the effect of the mixture design on the build-up of rigidity in the cement paste [40]. An analogous dependence was found by *Zhang* [43]: he reported diverse elastic modulus, E , hardness, H , and contact creep modulus, C_i , values for tricalcium silicate (C_3S) and dicalcium silicate (C_2S) pastes with the same porosity, remarking the importance of the solid phases, their volumetric distribution and the joints strength in controlling the final mechanical properties.

A multitude of creep theories have been proposed in the last century including, for example, the mechanical deformation theory, plastic theory, viscous and visco-elastic theory, solid solution theory, seepage theory, micro-cracking theory and long-term aging theory among many others [33–36]. However, none of them can explain all experimental observations and possible creep mechanisms. Since CaCO_3 cements lack the

amorphous C-S-H phase, the most probable creep mechanisms, according to the American Concrete Institute Committee [62], can be a combination of microcracking in the early stages and dissolution and precipitation of calcite when is it under pressure in the long-term.

Under microindentation tests, a small region of the sample is subjected to large compressive stresses. The origin of the non-logarithmic part of the creep functions (Figure 6B) might be ascribed to cracking or microcracking of CaCO_3 grain joints since many cementitious materials and rocks are known to be quasi brittle [48,63,64]. Thus, this mechanism is naturally affected by the amount and strength of grain joints. Similar time dependence for the growth of microcracks was reported by *Bazant* and co-workers for concrete samples [65]. Moreover, frictional grain boundary sliding may also occur if the frictional force between calcite grains is overcome, causing them to slide past each other [66]. However, this mechanism is more likely to occur at low effective stresses.

In the long-term, probably the best candidate to explain the creep of CaCO_3 cements is the so-called theory of dissolution, transport and precipitation under pressure (or pressure solution theory), which is considered to be the most important one to explain the time dependent deformation of rocks [67–69]. The theory stands that the macroscopic creep is a result of the geometry change of the solid matrix (e.g. crystals) at microscopic scale. This change is driven at the microscale by chemical potential differences between the stressed and unstressed part of the solid and is governed by a mass transfer that occurs in three steps: i) dissolution of solid under pressure, ii) diffusion of dissolved mass through the interface of crystals or their aggregates [70] in a very thin liquid film [71], and finally iii) precipitation at less stressed sites.

In this line, creep of CaCO_3 cements can be due to the local dissolution of calcite crystals when they are stressed. *Croize et al.* [72] claimed that the deformation of calcite monocrystals occurs either by dissolution and diffusion along the contact calcite/indenter interface, i.e., pressure solution, or by a combination of pressure solution and subcritical crack growth from the contact area toward less stressed parts of the crystal. It should be noted that calcite is a brittle mineral and the formation of microcracks on its surface under the indenter seems plausible. The authors also claimed that the occurrence of one or the other mechanism is not ruled by the applied stress but most likely by the presence or not of a flaw within the crystal. Thus, how the overall bridging area within a calcite crystal network regulate or influence the creep rate of CaCO_3 cements might be rationalized in the following way: a lower bridging area favours local stress concentration and thus the sample can exhibit more creep. Dissolved CaCO_3 grains can be transported and precipitated elsewhere. However, this process is much less likely to happen for larger overall contact areas since they will require higher loads to reach the same levels of stress concentration. For calcite monocrystals, the creep rate deformation has been reported to be diffusion-controlled [73] rather than dissolution-limited, despite of the low solubility of calcite. Therefore, a similar ruling step may be considered for calcite aggregates but further studies will be necessary to confirm this approach. In a similar way as for CaCO_3 cements, *Pachon-Rodriguez et al.* [74] showed that dissolution and precipitation under pressure is the main mechanism of creep of crystalline gypsum plaster.

In order to evaluate a possible upgrade of CaCO_3 cements to commercial production, a comparison of the creep and elastic parameters must be done with OPC. Microindentation tests were carried out by *Zhang et al.* for OPC samples [39]. A contact creep modulus, C_i , of ~ 20 GPa was reported for a cement sample (P50-0SV) with the same water to cement ratio as the CaCO_3 samples here tested ($w/p = 0.5$). That value is ~ 20 times larger than that obtained for the ACC:V = 1:1 wt.% composition, but only double than the measured for the ACC:V = 1:3 wt.% sample. Regarding the elastic modulus, E , the P50-0SV exhibited a value of about 11 GPa, whereas CaCO_3 values are 12 to 4 times lower with increasing initial vaterite weight fraction. Thus, even though the ACC:V = 1:3 wt.% composition shows the most similar properties, further strategies are still necessary to improve its performance before considering CaCO_3 cements for industrial applications.

3.3.2. Effect of relative humidity

Figure 7(E-H) shows the main variations of all measured parameters (contact creep modulus, C_i , characteristic creep time, τ_i , elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H) from microindentation tests on samples with diverse composition (ACC:V = 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.%) as function of the RH conditions tested. At a glance, Figure 7E shows that the contact creep modulus, C_i , of CaCO_3 cement samples breaks down dramatically (semilog scale) with RH regardless of the initial vaterite content, X_v , of the samples, i.e. larger moisture conditions make the samples softer, as expected. For example, for the specimen with composition ACC:V = 1:2 wt.%, the C_i drops dramatically from about 45 GPa at 33% RH to ~ 5 GPa at 54% RH and to ~ 0.1 GPa under 93% RH (See Table 1). The former drop corresponds to a factor 9 while the latter is over a factor 50. Nevertheless, even larger breakdowns have been reported previously for other cement pastes: a drop by a factor 100 was reported for C_i of gypsum plaster when moving from medium RH ($\sim 50\%$) towards water-saturated conditions ($\sim 100\%$) [43]. Moreover, in the same study a factor-12 drop was reported for calcium hydroxide compacts for the same ΔRH . On the other hand, much smaller breakdowns (factor 2) have been reported for C_3S and C-S-H compacts when moving from medium to high RH conditions [43], but those are radically different from the previous examples since their microstructure is highly amorphous. Thus, the amplitude of the creep rate of CaCO_3 cements increases exponentially with the RH, as it does for other crystalline binders.

Regarding the characteristic creep time, τ_i , from Figure 7F one observes that an increase of the moisture equilibrium of the samples derives to larger characteristic creep times, i.e. the samples require longer periods of time to reach logarithmic creep kinetics. The main drift between these two parameters is linear and has a slope of 1.6.

The effect of RH on the elastic modulus, E , and the hardness, H , of CaCO_3 cement samples with different X_v is shown on Figure 7G and H, respectively. At a glance, one observes that both follow a similar drift as the one obtained for the contact creep modulus, C_i ; i.e., a larger RH reduces the E and H of the samples, as expected. Indeed, they both follow a very similar trend since the slopes of their corresponding averaged fits are almost identical (-1.1 and -1.3 for E and H , respectively). Moreover, the insert in subplot H shows that hardness, H , of the samples increases linearly with the Young's modulus, E .

To understand the role of moisture equilibrium on creep behaviour for cementitious materials, one needs to focus on the porosity since the voids will be either empty or full of water depending on the RH conditions. As commented previously, the porosity of all CaCO₃ cements compositions here tested is very similar ($\phi = 39\%$), and a similar influence on the creep behaviour can be expected for all compositions. When a porous material dries, the larger pores desaturates firstly followed by the smallest ones. Indeed, the largest pore entry radius, r_{pe} , i.e., the largest pore which remains saturated for a porous material in moisture equilibrium with a given relative humidity, can be calculated by applying the *Kelvin-Laplace* law for drying with the following equation [75]:

$$r_{pe} = \frac{2 \gamma_{gl} \cos \theta}{RT/V_{m,H_2O} \ln RH} \quad (13)$$

where γ_{gl} is the air-water interface energy, T is the temperature, R is the ideal gas constant, θ is the wetting angle, V_{m,H_2O} is the molar volume of water and RH is the relative humidity at a given temperature. At a temperature $T = 295$ K, with $\gamma_{gl} = 73$ mJ/m², $\theta = 0$, $R = 8.31$ J/(mol·K) and $V_{m,H_2O} = 18$ cm³/mol, the relation between the relative humidity within the sample and the largest pore entry radius is presented in Figure 9. As can be observed, the lower the relative humidity is, the smaller this radius is.

Figure 9. Largest radius r_{pe} of pores remaining saturated at various relative humidity.

By applying Eq. 13 for the RH values here studied, the radius of the largest pores remaining saturated under each situation, r_{pe} , can be estimated. For 33%, 54% and 93% RH the corresponding values are ~ 1 nm, ~ 2 nm and ~ 10 nm, respectively. From this analysis, it seems that water in pores with an entry radius smaller than those values at each specific condition is linked to the long-term basic creep properties of CaCO₃ cements. In addition, a contribution from the water activity by itself cannot be discarded for this kind of material. The presence of more intergranular water might enhance the local dissolution of calcite and thus increase the amplitude of creep strains, in agreement with the pressure solution theory introduced above. Moreover, other mechanisms may be activated by the presence of fluids within the calcite network as the aforementioned frictional grain boundary sliding mechanism. Under this scenario, calcite dissolution can remove asperities and will reduce the friction between grains, making the creep amplitude to rise.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we have studied the compressive strength, the elasticity and the long-term creep properties of calcium carbonate cements with diverse microstructures, conditioned at several relative humidity. The results show that a larger starting amount of vaterite, X_v , within the mixture design derives on more elastic and resistant specimens due to the larger overall bridging area within the newly formed calcite crystals.

The micro-indentation results show that creep is logarithmic with respect to time, and hence the contact creep modulus, C_i , and the characteristic creep time, τ , could be extracted from each test. For a given relative humidity, the amplitude of creep strain decreases with increasing initial amount of vaterite, making the contact creep modulus, C_i , to rise on a linear manner with the elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , of the specimens. The differences among their properties must be due to their particular microstructure and the joint's strength among the CaCO_3 grains after the setting reaction. Moreover, the most probable creep mechanisms seem to be a combination of microcracking in the early stages and dissolution and reprecipitation of calcite in the long-term (also known as pressure solution theory).

On the other hand, for a given composition, the amplitude of creep grows with the increase of relative humidity, inducing the contact creep modulus, C_i , the elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , of the samples to decrease. The presence of water in pores with an entry radius smaller than 1nm, 2nm or 10nm under 33%, 54% and 93% RH conditions respectively, may enhance the local dissolution of calcite and explain the raise of the creep amplitude. This hypothesis is also in agreement with the pressure solution theory and support the fact that crystalline binders, such as our calcium carbonate cements, are more sensitive to the relative humidity than others which contain amorphous phases like C-S-H.

Furthermore, the results suggest that the mechanical properties of calcium carbonate cements are enforced when reducing the fraction of ACC in the mixture design. However, their mechanical properties become more sensitive to relative humidity, especially creep. These results are in accordance with the findings for C-S-H (amorphous) and gypsum (crystalline).

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 642976-NanoHeal Project. The results of this paper reflect only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. J.R.-S.- would like to express his thanks to Francois Renard (University of Oslo & Universite Grenoble-Alpes) for making possible the compressive strength tests, to Martin Mosquet and Quoc Huy Vu (both from Lafarge-Holcim Centre of Research) for their help to upgrade the micro-indenter and for various supports during the performance of the micro-indentation creep experiments.

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Supplementary Material

By introducing a fictitious indentation test with an instantaneous loading phase, an instantaneous unloading phase and an instantaneous-reloading-and holding phase, Vandamme *et al.* [53] derived a method to back-calculate creep properties from an indentation test in which time-independent plasticity occurs.

The main assumption in their derivation is that time independent plasticity occurs only during the loading phase but not during the holding nor unloading phases. Their demonstration starts by writing, in the case of elastic indentation, the contact radius, r_c , as a function of indentation depth: $r_c = f(h)$.

The analytical expression of the function f is not necessary in the derivation. Integrating Eq. 3 with respect to indentation depth, h , yields: $F = 2 M R(h)$; where $R(h)$ is the primitive function of $f(h)$ for which $R(0)=0$. Rewriting the yield expression in the time domain for a linear viscoelastic material by applying the correspondence principle, one obtains:

$$F(t) = 2 \int_0^t M(t - \tau) \frac{d}{d\tau} R(h(\tau)) d\tau \quad (\text{SM. 1})$$

Performing Laplace transform to Eq. SM. 1, one obtains:

$$\mathcal{L}(F(t)) = 2s \cdot \mathcal{L}(M(t))\mathcal{L}(R(h(t))) \quad (\text{SM. 2})$$

In the case of a step load, one can link the contact creep compliance, $L(t)$, to indentation data in Laplace domain. By performing inverse Laplace transform, one obtains the time-dependent contact creep compliance in the time domain as a function of indentation depth during the holding phase:

$$L(t) = \frac{2 R(h(t))}{F_{max}} \quad (\text{SM.3})$$

After differentiating Eq. SM. 3 with respect to time, one obtains the relation of interest which links the derivative of the contact creep compliance to the rate of penetration of the indentation probe during the holding phase [53]:

$$L'(t) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{2 R(h(t))}{F_{max}} \right) = \frac{2 f(h(t)) h'(t)}{F_{max}} = \frac{2 r_c(t) h'(t)}{F_{max}} \quad (\text{SM. 4})$$

where r_c is the radius the projected contact area, A_c . Excluding a flat punch, $r_c(t)$ evolves with h_c , but assuming that it does not change too much during the holding phase is realistic. Then, the contact radius during holding can therefore be estimated by the contact radius at the start of unloading and can be estimated by the Oliver and Pharr's method [51]. Integrating Eq. SM. 4 with respect to time from the beginning of holding phase yields:

$$L(t) - L(0) = L(t) - \frac{1}{M_0} = \frac{2 r_c \Delta h(t)}{F_{max}} \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta h(t)$ is the change of indentation depth during the holding phase. The difference $L(t) - L(0)$ between the contact creep compliance $L(t)$ and the reciprocal of indentation modulus $L(0) = 1/M_0$ at the moment of

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loading is termed the contact creep function. The use of Eq. 10 to back-calculate creep properties enables to obtain a contact compliance which is a material property.